

Spectrophotometric Studies on 5-Hydroxyindole, 5-Hydroxyindole-2-carboxylic Acid and 5-Hydroxyindole-3-acetic Acid

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Uv absorption spectral studies on 5-hydroxyindole (5HI), 5-hydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (5HI2AA) and 5-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (5HI3AA) have been carried out in aqueous solution in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states (200 Gy maximum dose). The possible chromophoric groups responsible for maximum absorption in the different wavelengths in the unirradiated compounds and in the radiolytic products have been indicated. The present hypochromicity of all these compounds at different absorption maxima at 100 Gy has been indicated. On comparison of our previous work on 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (HT) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) it is observed that the radiosensitivity can be arranged for all the compounds in the following order 5HI2AA > 5HI3AA > 5HI > 5HT > HT.

Effect of gamma irradiation on aqueous solution of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (HT) and 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) has been reported¹. Compounds like 5-hydroxyindole (5HI), 5-hydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (5HI2AA) and 5-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (5HI3AA) are produced by metabolism or radiolysis^{2,3} of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan and 5-hydroxytryptamine. The metabolic products of 5HT like 5HI2AA, 5HI3AA and 5HI are present in the extracellular portion of hippocampus or brain cortex. Their amount varies depending upon the constraint placed upon the experimental animals^{4–6}. Since gamma radiation can induce changes to these compounds which will be biologically important it has been thought worthwhile to find out gamma radiation-induced sensitivity of all these compounds.

Results and Discussion

5HI shows (Fig. 1) three maxima at 198 nm, slightly more than 220 nm and at 275 nm respectively. The values of absorption intensity for 5HI solutions irradiated to 20 and 50 Gy are more compared to unirradiated solution in the wavelength range up to 200 nm. But for higher doses of 100 and 200 Gy the absorption intensities are less compared to unirradiated solution. With increase in gamma radiation dose in the range 20–200 Gy, the intensity of absorption decreases at 220 and 275 nm but the maximum at 198 nm disappears with irradiation. With increase in dose the intensity of absorption in

the wave-length range 190–210 nm decreases compared to control for doses in the range 50–200 Gy. The percentage hypochromicity at 220 and 275 nm at 100 Gy are 36 and 22% respectively. Moreover, there is consistent decrease in pH with increasing dose (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Uv absorption spectra of 5-hydroxyindole (concn. = 10 μ M): (O) unirradiated, pH 4.50, (●) dose 20 Gy, pH 4.48, (x) dose 50 Gy, pH 4.43, (Δ) dose 100 Gy, pH 4.37 and (□) dose 200 Gy, pH 4.14.

5HI2AA in the unirradiated state shows absorption maximum at 215 and 290 nm. With increase in radiation dose to the compound there is consistent decrease in absorbance intensity at both these wavelengths (Fig. 2). The percentage hypochromicity at 215 and 290 nm at 100 Gy are 74.7 and 76.7% (Table 1). The variation in pH with dose is insignificant. Fig. 3 shows the uv absorption

spectra of 5HI3AA in unirradiated and gamma irradiated states. The unirradiated compound shows two maxima at 202 and 270 nm along with a shoulder at 210 nm. With increase in radiation dose the

Fig. 2. Uv absorption spectra of 5-hydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (concn. = 10 μM) : (O) unirradiated, pH 5.40, (●) dose 10 Gy, pH 5.42, (●) dose 20 Gy, pH 5.45, (Δ) dose 50 Gy, pH 5.47, (⊗) dose 100 Gy, pH 5.43 and (□) dose 200 Gy, pH 5.43.

absorption maxima at 202 nm disappears above 20 Gy, the shoulder takes the shape of a peak at 50 Gy which again disappears with higher dose. The absorption intensity decreases at all the wavelengths

Fig. 3. Uv absorption spectra of 5-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (concn. = 10 μM) : (O) unirradiated, pH 5.52, (●) dose 10 Gy, pH 5.47, (Δ) dose 20 Gy, pH 5.30, (▲) dose 50 Gy, pH 5.20, (□) dose 100 Gy, pH 5.07 and (■) dose 200 Gy, pH 4.90.

consistently with increase in dose. The variation in pH is consistent with dose increment. The percentages hypochromicity at 202, 222 and 275 nm for a

maximum dose of 100 Gy have been found to be 20.7, 43.5 and 40% respectively.

From our previous work¹, the observed percentage hypochromicity at 207, 220 and 275 nm are 7.50, 12 and 14% for 5HT and 6.52, 2.32 and 8.33% for HT respectively (Table 1). The absorption maximum of 5HI at 275 nm can be attributed to indole ring, the shoulder above 220 nm can be attributed to pyrrole ring. Reported value for indole ring is at 265 nm and that for pyrrole ring is at 210 nm in hexane⁷. It appears in polar solvent like water the maxima have shifted. However, the hydroxyl group attached to indole is an auxochrome⁸. Radiation-induced cleavage near the double bond in the second and third positions of pyrrole ring with increasing dose is clearly indicated. The degradation product formed up to a dose of 50 Gy probably contains C=C-C≡N as the chromophoric group, since the λ_{max} = 215 nm is for this chromophore⁸. The formation of this chromophore has been supported by ir studies on 5HT. 5HT when irradiated to a dose of 15 Gy does not show any peak in the irradiated state whereas unirradiated compound shows 82% absorbance at 2 100 cm⁻¹. This indicates formation of -C≡N from 5HT cleavage. As a result of gamma

TABLE 1—COMPARISON OF PERCENTAGE HYPOCHROMICITY OF 5HI2AA, 5HI3AA, 5HI, 5HT and HT AT 100 Gy AND CONCENTRATION 10 μM

Compd. λ _{max} (nm)	Absorbance		
	Unirradiated	Irradiated	% Hypochromicity
5HI			
220	0.22	0.14	36
270	0.09	0.07	22
5HI2AA			
215	0.79	0.20	74.7
290	0.43	0.10	76.7
5HI3AA			
202	0.24	0.19	20.7
222	0.23	0.13	43.5
275	0.07	0.05	40.0
5HT			
207	2.58	2.48	7.50
220	2.35	2.07	12.00
275	0.55	0.47	14.00
HT			
207	2.30	2.15	6.52
220	2.15	2.10	2.32
275	0.65	0.60	8.33

irradiation opening of the double bond in 5HI in between second and third carbon atom takes place⁹. The consistent decrease in pH with increasing dose can be ascribed to increased production of COOH group from the cleavage of the double bond in the 2,3-position of 5HI.

The maxima at 215 and 290 nm for 5HI2AA (Fig. 2) can be explained as due to the absorption of indole ring and CH₂COOH group in 2-position of indole ring. The decrease in absorbance with dose at both the wavelengths are comparable (Table 1). Hence radiation-induced damage to both the chromophores are almost same.

For 5HI3AA, the shoulder at 202 nm and absorption maximum at 222 and 275 nm in the unirradiated solution can be attributed to cyclopentadiene structure (λ_{\max} 200 nm, ϵ_{\max} 10000 in hexane), indole ring (λ_{\max} 215 nm, ϵ_{\max} 25000) and (λ_{\max} 265 nm, ϵ_{\max} 6300 in hexane), >C=C-C=O chromophoric group (λ_{\max} 224 nm, ϵ_{\max} 9750 in ethanol)⁷.

The slight differences in the absorption maxima obtained experimentally and that cited in literature may be explained as due to polarity of solvent used. With increase in dose there is a scission of the ionisable carboxyl group first and then the double bond in the 2,3-position breaks up producing carboxylic acid. This is the likely reason for the consistent decrease in pH with increasing dose.

The different percentage hypochromicity as noted earlier for a dose of 100 Gy (Table 1) indicates that sensitivity of the different chromophores towards radiation dose is different. Radiation-induced damage to the side-chain and double bond in the indole ring are comparable.

The electron affinity at 2- and 3-positions of 5-hydroxyindole are different. Hence the bond strength of the CH₂COOH group attached to the second and third position of 5-hydroxyindole should be different. Radiation-induced changes from these two positions have been found to be different.

For a comparison of the hypochromicity values at 220, 215 and 275 or 290 nm for all these compounds for a dose of 100 Gy (Table 1), the radiosensitivity of these compounds can be given in the order : 5HI2AA > 5HI3AA > 5HI > 5HT > HT.

Experimental

5-Hydroxyindole (5HI), 5-dihydroxyindole-2-carboxylic acid (5HI2AA) and 5-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (5HI3AA) (Sigma) were used. The compounds were dissolved in hot water. Gamma irradiations of the solutions (concentration 10 μ M) of all the compounds were done in a Gamma cell 220 of Atomic Energy of Canada. Dose rate was 2.6 Gy min⁻¹ as determined by a standard methodology¹⁰. Uv absorption study was done by a Carl-Zeiss PMQII spectrophotometer where absorbance could be measured upto 0.005 unit. Special care was taken for measuring absorbances in the wavelength range 190–220 nm by keeping the cuvettes in nitrogen atmosphere.

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